
161. Strongly lensed quasars

GAIA DATA RELEASE 3 was issued in June 2022, and the next major release, DR4, is not scheduled until 2025. But on 10 October 2023, the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium (DPAC) published five papers forming part of a special ‘**Focused Product Release**’. I looked at the first four in essays 157–160.

The fifth, by Krone-Martins et al. (2023), is a new search for strongly lensed quasars, which I look at here.

I HAVE already discussed the application of Gaia data to quasar research in previous essays, notably their role in defining the celestial reference frame (essay 27), and consequently in detecting Galactic aberration (essay 32), and perhaps our Galaxy’s ‘tumbling’ disk within the dark matter halo (essay 95). In addition, of just over 1 million previously known quasars analysed in DR3, a host galaxy was detected around 65 000 (essay 82).

Already by the end of 2020, nearly 100 publications had used the DR1 or DR2 data to examine the reliability of earlier quasar surveys, and to quantify effects important in refining the extragalactic reference frame link.

AS AN ASIDE to the main topic of this essay, and in an attempt to bring the Gaia/quasar research field more up-to-date, let me mention the Gaia–unWISE all-sky quasar catalogue, Quaia (Storey-Fisher et al., 2023).

This merges the 6 649 162 quasar candidates from Gaia DR3 having redshift estimates from its low-resolution BP/RP spectra (Delchambre et al., 2023) with the **unWISE infrared catalogue** (reprocessed from WISE) to construct a large volume spectroscopic quasar sample suitable for cosmological studies. It has 1 295 502 quasars with $G < 20.5$ mag, and 755 850 candidates in an even more well-defined sample to $G < 20.0$ mag.

Amongst its application, Alonso et al. (2023) examined the angular clustering of the quasars to derive cosmological constraints on the amplitude and growth of structure, importantly breaking the usual degeneracy between the matter density parameter (Ω_m) and the amplitude of the matter power spectrum (σ_8), yielding $\Omega_m = 0.343^{+0.017}_{-0.019}$ and $\sigma_8 = 0.766 \pm 0.034$.

AN IMPORTANT contribution of Gaia to quasar science is in detecting and classifying gravitationally lensed systems (essays 16 and 58). On-board CCD sampling provides source images with an ultimate resolution of 0.1–0.2 arcsec in the scan direction, much better than can be routinely measured from ground. Accordingly, Gaia is able to discover new (and numerous) lensed quasars with image separations below ~ 1 arcsec.

Strongly lensed quasars, i.e. those which result in multiple *discrete* images, provide an important diagnostic for many applications. These include measuring the Hubble constant at intermediate cosmic distances (Chen et al., 2019; Shajib et al., 2020); constraining the properties of dark matter (Gilman et al., 2019; Nierenberg et al., 2020); inferring structure near the event horizon of supermassive black holes (Pooley et al., 2009; Chartas et al., 2016); measuring the accretion disk size (Blackburne et al., 2011; Fian et al., 2021); constraining the quasar broad emission-line region geometry (Sluse et al., 2011; Braibant et al., 2017); measuring black hole spin (Walton et al., 2015; Middleton, 2016); and testing general relativity in the strong-gravity regime (Collett et al., 2018; Melo-Carneiro et al., 2023).

Amongst the most keenly hunted are the quadruply-imaged ‘Einstein crosses’ (essay 58), which are some of the most constraining for detailed physical modelling.

TO give a flavour of the ongoing studies, a series of papers ‘Gaia GraL’ (for gravitational lensing) has focussed on the lensed systems discovered in Gaia DR2.

These have dealt with: new quadruple candidates around known quasars (Krone-Martins et al., 2018); the statistics of previously known quadruple-image quasars, where 12 systems were found to have all four images detected (Ducourant et al., 2018); a systematic blind search for new lensed systems (Delchambre et al., 2019); ground-based confirmation and modelling of new discoveries (Wertz et al., 2019; Krone-Martins et al., 2019; Stern et al., 2021); XMM–Newton X-ray observations of discoveries between $z = 1–3$ (Connor et al., 2022); and a radio census of 24 lensed systems (Dobie et al., 2023).

A COMPILATION of known lenses (with images) is held at research.ast.cam.ac.uk/lensedquasars. Of these, for example, some 80 quadruple-image systems are known today (Stern et al., 2021).

Most lensed systems currently known have image separations above 1 arcsec (e.g. Ducourant et al., 2018). Nevertheless, the expected distribution of lenses is estimated to peak at somewhat smaller separations, below 1 arcsec, making most of them more-or-less undetectable from the ground.

Estimates of the lensed quasars detectable by Gaia (in standard Λ CDM cosmology) have suggested that ~ 3000 multiply imaged quasars could be detected, of which > 250 would have ≥ 3 images and the rest doubles (Finet & Surdej, 2016). By providing a homogeneous survey at ~ 180 mas angular resolution, and with precise astrometry for all lensed images, Gaia should yield a significant increase in the number of known lensed systems.

But even the GDR2 and GDR3 catalogues are known to be incomplete at separations $\lesssim 2$ arcsec (Arenou et al., 2017; Arenou et al., 2018; Fabricius et al., 2021). This is the result of a robust selection on the astrometric and photometric quality indicators of the published sources.

CAPITALISING ON Gaia's unprecedented angular resolution of ~ 0.18 arcsec in the optical, and in order to improve the completeness of lensing searches at small angular separations, Krone-Martins et al. (2023) developed the GravLens pipeline, implemented within the Gaia DPAC Consortium. Their goal was to analyse all Gaia detections around quasars, and to produce a catalogue of secondary sources around each of them, along with their mean astrometry and photometry.

Their dedicated processing started from an input list of quasars, resulting from the merger of a number of major catalogues of quasars and AGN (active galactic nuclei) candidates, including the Milliquas catalogue (Flesch, 2021); the R90 and C75 selections of the ALLWISE catalogue (Assef et al., 2018); a catalogue of AGN candidates (Shu et al., 2019); a subset of the GDR3 quasar candidates (Bailer-Jones et al., 2023); and additional quasars whose morphology was analysed by Ducourant et al. (2023). Most contain stellar contaminants. Their resulting starting list contained 3 760 480 quasars or quasar candidates with an entry in GDR3.

Of the data from the first 3 years of operations, corresponding to the time interval of DR3, they analysed 183 368 062 transits matched to the 3 760 480 quasars from their initial list. GravLens then identified all Gaia transits within 6 arcsec of each quasar, based on machine-learning (specifically the DBSCAN unsupervised clustering algorithm), and without relying on the standard Gaia object cross-matching. The output is a list of sources within 6 arcsec of each quasar, with mean positions, fluxes, and magnitudes of the components.

Distribution of quasars in the input list, in Galactic coordinates.

THEY FOUND a total of 4 760 920 sources, including the quasars themselves, within 6 arcsec of the quasar positions. Of these, 103 000 are new sources complementing those already present in GDR3. In most cases (87%), the quasar is a single source, without close neighbour. In 501 385 cases, neighbouring sources were detected, of which 9% have two components. There are 159 000 systems (4%) with more than two components. They also found 9000 multiplets with more than 10 components, generally corresponding to extended galaxies decomposed into many sources.

Their resulting GravLens catalogue includes 450 known or candidate lenses previously published in the literature, 76 with four images, and the rest being two-component systems. For 67 of the 76 quadruple systems, GravLens complements the existing measures from GDR3 by measuring one or more additional components, or the deflecting galaxy itself. In total it found 1293 components in the fields of known lenses, of which 1207 were present in GDR3. The 86 newly detected components in the fields of known lenses are mostly faint components surrounding lenses with a small number of existing GDR3 counterparts.

To search for new lenses, they employed two methods: an outlier 'scoring' algorithm, and an application of the Extremely Randomised Trees algorithm (Delchambre et al., 2019), making use of Gaia spectra when available. They identified 381 new lensed candidates, of which they considered 49 as the most promising. These have angular sizes from 1.03–5.97 arcsec, with a minimum image separation of 0.41 arcsec.

Two examples of the Gaia multiple-lens detections (Krone-Martins et al., 2023; Figs 3 and 8b)